

Supplementary Fig. S2 The read mapping deviations due to divergence between CDC Landmark and CDC Stanley present on chromosome 3A are also observed in DH plants derived from CDC Stanley X CDC Landmark. Landmark470 and Stanley470 are high coverage WGS used in developing the respective reference genome. LandmarkDH and StanleyDH are used in developing StanleyLandmarkDH populations. The read mapping variations present in CDC Stanley when mapped to CDC Landmark are observed on the genomic segments with blue allele in DH plants. Each panel shows the genomic position of a given chromosome in 1Mb bins on the physical map of the CDC Landmark reference genome in the x-axis with points showing the normalized number of reads mapping to the respective bin. The vertical axis shows both normalized read count (left) and chromosome dosage (right). The parental allele for individual SNP variants is shown on top for CDC Landmark (red) and CDC Stanley (blue) alleles. Centromere positions are showing as black triangle.